

Monitoring of nature infrastructure - Skill acquisition fOr NATure-bAsed solutions

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The EU's Green Deal highlights the Sustainable Use Regulation (SUR) and Nature Restoration Law (NRL) as essential for sustainable farming, food security, and environmental resilience. Scientific evidence is needed to support their long-term benefits. Integrating Nature-based Solutions (NbS) into this framework further strengthens its vision, offering a cost-effective approach to achieving biodiversity and climate targets while promoting sustainable agriculture and resource management. In Serbia, the EU-funded Twinning Green Deal SONATA project aims to map and assess natural and semi-natural features, known as Nature Infrastructure (NI). This initiative leverages data from in-situ observations, satellites, the Internet of Things (IoT), and advanced technologies such as cloud computing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to improve data quality and availability with the broader aim of supporting biodiversity and climate action planning through NbS.

Modelling, Mapping, and Monitoring Nature Infrastructure (3M NI) is an evolving land use and management strategy that integrates digital technologies and biodiversity knowledge to promote the sustainable use of resources. SONATA focuses on habitats within and around agricultural landscapes, examining how habitat mapping and NbS implementation can optimize crop yield and pollinator biodiversity while also making the region more resilient to the effects of climate change. A key aspect of NbS allocation and implementation planning is societal involvement, ensuring that it reflects local needs and priorities through participatory approaches such as the Living Lab (LL) concept. However, economic, technological, and social challenges have slowed the adoption of 3M NI and LivingLabs practice in southeastern Europe, leading to lower uptake and higher societal and monetary costs. To address these barriers, SONATA unites several European organizations in collaboration with BIOS in Serbia to develop a capacity-building strategy and enhance regional implementation efforts for NbS.